

AUTOMATIC GENERATION OF IMAGES FROM HURRICANE VOLUME DATA THROUGH EVOLUTIONARY OPTIMIZATION

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Introduction and study objectives

The study of hurricanes through information visualization and visual analysis is useful for tracking and understanding the behavior and impact of such hazardous natural phenomena. Images obtained from data commonly acquired through meteorological radar provide scientists with a visual representation of the storm's characteristics, such as its location, size, and intensity. Such information is useful for forecasting, decision making in disaster management and environmental and human health risk assessment. Visual representations of such phenomena can help emergency responders and policymakers make informed decisions about evacuations, disaster response, and resource allocation. In this context, we propose an automated means of generating representations from complex 3D datasets obtained from meteorological radar scans of regions affected by hurricanes. Our data represents a region of space of approximately 2000x2000x20 km, scanned during hurricane Isabel (a category 5 hurricane on the Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Wind Scale) one of the many hurricanes which affected the North-American East coast for over 2 weeks. The resulting data set is a 3D regular grid of numeric values, each representing the water vapor mixing ratio (g/kg) in its corresponding spatial position. Our objective is to develop a means to automatically generate images from such data, illustrating the geometry and spatial features of the aforementioned phenomenon.

Methodology

Our approach is based on a direct volume renderer, which is a computational method of generating 2D representations from 3D volumetric data. The visualization pipeline involves iterating through the data using a ray casting method, i.e. a means of sampling a 3D region of space from the perspective of the observer. From each pixel in the output image, we cast a ray through the volume dataset and take multiple data samples along each ray. Subsequently, we employ a transfer function to map the data values of the samples to colors and opacities. We then combine the color and opacity values along each ray, resulting in the corresponding pixel color. The key aspect of this approach is defining the transfer function such that the mapped colors and opacities result in images which are representative of the underlying data. We define the transfer function as a piecewise 3rd degree polynomial, where each component (or “piece”) is specified locally as $f:[0,1]:[0,1]$, $f(u) = -2u^3 + 3u^2$. We define a *control point* as a point at either end of such component. Thus, the overall shape of the function can be specified by defining coordinates for the control points, which, in turn, can be used to control the distribution of colors and opacities throughout the volume. In order to automate the

specification of the transfer function, we employ a genetic algorithm to search through the space of control points. We define the structure of the chromosome as real valued vector $[D_1, R_1, G_1, B_1, A_1, D_2, R_2, G_2, B_2, A_2, \dots, D_n, R_n, G_n, B_n, A_n]$, where n is the number of control points, and D_i, R_i, G_i, B_i, A_i are the data value, red, green, blue and opacity values of control point i , respectively. Throughout the iterations of the genetic approach, we use random uniform mutation and single-point crossover operators. For the optimization objective, we first determine the positions at which the cumulative opacity reaches a specified threshold (i.e. the point at which the corresponding surface becomes clearly visible). At such positions, we compute the dot product between the gradient vector and the viewing vector (the vector indicating the direction toward the observer). The result is a map of gradient orientations with respect to the viewing direction. We compute the histogram of the values from this map and perform a χ^2 test of the corresponding distribution against the equivalent uniform distribution resulting from the mean value of the histogram. We formulate the fitness function such that the resulting χ^2 score is minimized, so that surfaces with a wide range of gradient angles are favored.

Results and conclusions

The previously-described genetic algorithm tends to favor transfer functions that highlight surfaces with a wide array of geometric features, as resulting from a close-to-uniform gradient angle distribution. Fig. 1 illustrates a few examples of images resulting from the abovementioned approach, rendered using transfer functions with control points chosen from the last population determined by the genetic algorithm. Considering our definition of the optimization objective, the method generates images which display objects from the volume data with diverse spatial features. We find that this is suitable for hurricane data, as the resulting images tend to display important spatial characteristics of this phenomenon, such as the “arms” of the hurricane, its vortice-like shape and its tendency to arrange in a spiral along the altitude. This information is useful for determining significant properties of the hurricane, such as its direction, its force and destructive potential, and, consequently, its impact and associated risks.

Fig. 1. Images rendered using transfer functions automatically determined by the genetic algorithm such that surfaces exhibiting highly-diverse features are favored.

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